

Perceived Challenges and Benefits of Contextualized CS1 Materials: Insights from African Higher Education Faculty

Survey Questions

- How do you perceive the importance of developing and incorporating contextually appropriate computing education materials for CS1 in African universities? Please elaborate on your answer where possible.
NB: Contextualized materials in this study context refer to teaching resources and examples that are designed to make computer science concepts more relatable and relevant by integrating cultural, or local contexts into the curriculum.
- Do you currently incorporate any contextualized materials in your teaching? If so, how? Give specific examples where possible. If you haven't used this approach yourself, feel free to share experiences you have witnessed or are aware of.
- How do you perceive the effectiveness of the contextualized materials you reviewed from our team when implemented in your classroom? Do you believe they address the learning needs of students from diverse cultural backgrounds effectively in your class?
- How do you perceive the integration of cultural elements (e.g., tribes, poems, music, food, games, languages, and lifestyle) into the CS1 materials? Do you think this approach effectively enhances student understanding and engagement with learning programming, particularly in African contexts? Can you share an example where possible?
- Given that the materials aim to develop key CS1 learning outcomes (e.g., iteration, conditionals, functions, and data structures), do you think the objectives are well-aligned with the cultural examples provided? Are there any areas where you feel the cultural content may distract or conflict with the learning objectives?
- What specific improvements or modifications would you suggest to enhance the contextualized materials for better alignment with your teaching philosophy and student needs? How could the design or content of these materials be tailored to reflect local cultures or experiences more effectively? Feel free to be as elaborative as possible by also giving examples where possible.
- In your opinion, is there a role of universities and higher education institutions in Africa when it comes to facilitating the integration of contextualised materials into computing courses? What institutional changes would help support the widespread adoption of such materials?
- What do you believe are the long-term benefits of integrating contextualized materials into computing education if any? How do you see this impacting students' career readiness, critical thinking, and problem-solving skills, especially in the context of globalized technology?